

Synthesis, Reactions, Mass Spectra and Biological Evaluation of some New 4-Aryloxymethylcarbostyrils

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Carbostyrils exhibit various biological activities¹. The present investigation reports the synthesis and reactions of some 4-phenoxyethylcarbostyrils (**2**). Anti-inflammatory activity of **2** has also been evaluated by the formalin induced rat paw edema method².

4-Bromomethylcarbostyril³ (**1**) reacted with various phenols to give 4-phenoxyethylcarbostyrils (**2**). The amide carbonyl of **2b** was found to react with the active methylene group of barbituric acid resulting in the condensed product (**3**) analogous to other carbostyrils⁴. Azo coupling of the 2-naphthyl ether (**4**) with the diazonium salt of *p*-toluidine resulted in the formation of **5**. The position of coupling was confirmed by the direct synthesis of azoether (**5**) by the reaction of **1** with 1-(*p*-tolylazo)-2-naphthol⁴ (Scheme 1).

Results and Discussion

In the ir spectra all the 4-phenoxyethylcarbostyrils (**2**; Table 1) showed C=O stretching band at 1660–1680 cm⁻¹. In the pmr spectra all the protons resonated at expected fields, and the NH proton appeared as a broad signal around 11.5 ppm. Mass spectra for **2a**, **b-e** showed the base at *m/z* 130. In the chemical ionisation spectra (*M*+*H*) ions were observed as base peaks in all cases.

Biological activity : Preliminary toxicity studies of compounds **2** on mice showed that all the test compounds possessed a LD₅₀ value of 1000 mg/kg when administered

intraperitoneally as 2% CMC suspensions. At doses above 600 mg/kg, the animals showed slight dysfunction in motor coordination, moderate depression and reduced movement.

Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity was carried out² employing phenylbutazone as standard. Inhibition of inflammation was measured at various intervals of time up to 24 h (Table 1). Some of the compounds, as indicated by the present results, exhibited activity comparable to phenylbutazone.

Substituents in the aryloxy moiety have considerable influence on the activity of the molecule. The 4'-methyl derivative (**2b**) showed a quick onset of action, and the peak activity was observed at the end of 2 h. Further, it has also been found to retain considerable activity at the end of 12 and 24 h. Monohalogenation increased the activity but reduced the retention of activity at the end of 24 h. Peak activity was found at 2 h for the monohalogenated ethers **2c** and **2d**. Introduction of the two or three halogens led to a substantial increase in activity and they exhibited peak activity at the end of 4 h in the case of **2f** and **2g**.

Most of these compounds did not show any significant analgesic activity in the Eddy's hot plate method⁵ and failed to provide protection against diphenylhydramine induced convulsions in albino mice, at dose levels of 500 and 200 mg/kg respectively.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY DATA AT DIFFERENT TIME INTERVALS OF COMPOUNDS **2***

Compd no	R	M p **	% Inhibition at different time intervals (h)						
			0.5	1	2	4	8	12	24
2a	H	198–99 ^a		-	-	-	-	-	-
b	4'-CH ₃	231–32 ^a	7.7	18.7	34.7	33.3	25.0	23.0	11.5
c	4'-Cl	210–11 ^b	-	12.5	39.1	37.5	33.3	15.4	3.7
d	2'-Cl	225–26 ^b	-	6.2	34.7	29.2	16.5	11.5	-
e	2', 4'-Cl	243–44 ^c	7.7	18.7	30.4	41.6	20.8	15.4	3.7
f	2', 4', 5', -Cl	262–63 ^c	-	6.2	31.8	41.7	20.8	11.6	-
g	2', 4', 6'-Br	275–76 ^c	-	6.2	30.4	41.7	20.8	11.5	-
Standard	-	-	7.7	18.7	39.1	41.7	25.0	19.2	7.7

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses **Crystallised from ^aC₆H₆, ^bC₆H₆ + pet ether, ^cAcOH **2h** (R = 2' -OCH₃), m p 195–96^o, not evaluated for anti-inflammatory activity

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.p.s. were taken in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian 90 and 270 MHz spectrometers using TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a Varian Mat CH7 instrument at 70 meV using direct insertion.

4-Phenoxymethylcarbostyrils (2a-i). *General method* : To a suspension of **1** (0.02 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.02 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was added the appropriate phenol (0.02 mol). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h, then cooled and filtered. The separated solid was treated with HCl (1 : 1, 50 ml), and the residual solid was washed with excess water and crystallised from a suitable solvent (Table 1) : yields 70–80%; δ (DMSO- d_6) **2a** 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.6 (1H, s, 3-CH), 7.0–7.8 (9H, m, ArH), 11.3 (1H, s, NH); **b** 2.2 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.6 (1H, s, 3-CH), 7.1–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 11.7 (1H, s, NH); **e** 5.2 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.5 (1H, s, 3-CH), 7.0–7.7 (7H, m, ArH), 11.4 (1H, s, NH); **h** 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.3 (2H, s, CH₂O), 6.6 (1H, s, 3-CH), 7.0–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 11.4 (1H, s, NH).

Reaction of 2b with barbituric acid. Formation of **3** : Condensation of **2b** with barbituric acid in a mixture of acetic anhydride and acetic acid according to literature method³ (40%), m.p. 244–45°d (AcOH); ν_{\max} 1 660 cm⁻¹ (CO); λ_{\max} (log ϵ) (AcOH) 380 (4.4), 475 (3.9), 510 nm (3.7).

4-(2'-Naphthyloxymethyl)carbostyril (4) : It was synthesised according to the general method given for compound **2** with the exception that KOH was used in place of K₂CO₃ : yield 40%, m.p. 281–82° (toluene); ν_{\max} 1 660 cm⁻¹ (CO).

Coupling of 4 with p-toluidine. Formation of **5** : To a suspension of **4** (0.05 M) in aqueous NaOH (10%, 5 ml) at 0° was added a solution of *p*-toluidinediazonium chloride (0.01 mol) slowly with stirring. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 30 min at room temperature, diluted with water and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid to obtain **5** (40%), m.p. 231–32°d (AcOH).

Reaction of 1 with 1-(o-tolyazo)-2-naphthol. Formation of **5** : To a suspension of 1-(*p*-tolylazo)-2-naphthol (0.01 mol) and **1**, powdered anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.01 mol) in dry acetone was added. The reaction mixture was stirred for 12 h, refluxed for about 4 h and left overnight. The separated solid was treated with HCl (1 : 1; 30 ml). The residual solid was crystallised from AcOH to obtain **5**. The compounds by both the methods were the same as confirmed by their m.m.p. and ir spectra.

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